

Bridging Internet of Things and Beyond 5G with Secure Orchestration

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Abstract—Orchestration technologies play a central role in managing the complexity of modern network systems, especially in IoT and B5G environments. This paper focuses on security orchestration in IoT for 5G and provides an overview of existing work, highlighting its contributions and identifying gaps that require further research. Key initiatives and projects such as SELFNET, INSPIRE 5G-PLUS, 5G-ENSURE, ANASTACIA and RAINBOW as well as open source platforms such as OpenBaton, OSM and ONAP are discussed to demonstrate the breadth of ongoing efforts in this area. Relevant standards from organizations such as ETSI, IETF, 5G PPP, NGMN and IEEE are analyzed in terms of their role in promoting interoperability and innovation. Finally, we summarize the experiences from current projects and standardization efforts and highlight the unresolved challenges and future research directions. Sustainability, scalability and the integration of advanced technologies remain critical for effective orchestration in next-generation networks.

Index Terms—IoT, B5G, network management, closed loop.

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing complexity of networked systems and the proliferation of IoT devices in the era of 5G have highlighted the importance of effective orchestration technologies. Orchestration involves the automated coordination and management of various network functions, services and resources to ensure seamless operations. With the advent of 5G technologies, the demand for robust, scalable and secure orchestration mechanisms has increased significantly. Orchestration refers to the automated arrangement, coordination and management of complex systems, processes and services. In the context of networks, orchestration is essential to optimize resource allocation, manage service lifecycles and ensure security and reliability in diverse and dynamic environments. As networks evolve with the introduction of 5G and IoT, orchestration has become a greater challenge due to the scale, heterogeneity and critical nature of these systems. Orchestration solutions must not only handle service provisioning and scaling, but also cross-domain interactions and real-time adaptability.

The taxonomy of orchestration can be divided into several main categories, each focusing on specific aspects of network management: Service Orchestration takes care of the provisioning and management of services in a network and ensures their seamless operation. Resource Orchestration focuses

on the allocation and optimization of physical and virtual resources within the network. Lifecycle Service Orchestration manages the entire lifecycle of network services, from creation to decommissioning, ensuring operational continuity. Security Orchestration (SCO) deals with the integration of security measures into the orchestration process to ensure the protection of services and resources. In modern network environments, orchestration often spans multiple domains, e.g. different organizations, geographical locations or technologies. Multi-domain orchestration is about coordinating these different elements to provide end-to-end functionality while ensuring security, performance and reliability. This aspect of orchestration is critical to enable interoperability and scalability in 5G and IoT ecosystems.

This paper provides a comprehensive exploration of orchestration technologies, underscoring the importance of orchestration in addressing security challenges specific to IoT ecosystems and 5G networks, reviewing existing solutions, identifying gaps, and emphasizing the need for scalable, adaptive, and efficient mechanisms. A detailed analysis of key projects such as SELFNET, INSPIRE 5G-PLUS and ANASTACIA is presented, as well as open source platforms such as OpenBaton, ONAP and OSM. In addition, the role of standardization organizations such as ETSI, IETF and IEEE in promoting innovation and interoperability is examined in detail. By synthesizing insights from projects, standards and emerging solutions, the paper identifies key findings, highlights unresolved research issues and suggests future directions for the advancement of orchestration technologies. Overall, we provide a foundational resource for understanding the current state, challenges, and opportunities of orchestration technologies for next-generation networks.

II. SECURITY ORCHESTRATION IN IOT FOR 5G TECHNOLOGIES

The IoT realizes a fully connected world with humans and things communicating with each other. The primary goal of IoT is to make every device accessible from the internet. The future internet will facilitate communication capabilities to any object with the potential of possessing computing and sensory

abilities to communicate with other devices. IoT consists of notions like Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN), Machine-to-Machine (M2M) communications, Low power Wireless Personal Area Networks (LoWPAN), or technologies like Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID) [1]. IoT, therefore, consists of billions of heterogeneous devices interacting with one another and producing a vast amount of diverse data flow. The increased connectivity results in huge security concerns and has significantly increased the potential attacks surfaces for cyber attacks.

Addressing the security issues in IoT is very challenging due to several reasons. Firstly, IoT nodes are resource-constrained and have limited storage, power, and computational capabilities. Secondly, considering the diverse nature of IoT devices, which range from sophisticated industrial machinery to basic wearable sensors, will result in different security requirements and interfaces [2]. Traditional security measures and protocols are not ideal for IoT environments because they cannot handle unexpected adaptability and interoperability issues. They do not fulfil the demands such as lightness and responsiveness required in IoT [3]. A single security function cannot eliminate the various security concerns mentioned above. However, the introduction of multiple security functions in a constrained IoT node and gateway is still questionable. Given these various security concerns, it will not be easy to realize the expected deployment of IoT solutions in different scenarios.

There is a need for advanced and adaptable novel security management frameworks to address the challenges of IoT that ensure an appropriate level of security in a dynamic nature and enable system resilience through self-repair and self-healing capabilities. Whenever a cyberattack or cyberthreat occurs in the managed IoT network, these mechanisms should orchestrate the defence against it. The benefits introduced by SDN and NFV can potentially change the cybersecurity landscape for IoT systems by providing additional scalability and flexibility needed to handle massive IoT deployments [4], thereby deploying or decommissioning on-demand VSFs. Orchestration of SDN controllers, NFV managers and IoT controllers requires a novel holistic, context-aware security architecture that enables dynamic reconfiguration, security chaining and customization of VSFs. The use of NFV and SDN, edge computing and IoT can significantly improve network connectivity at the network edge. NFV offers extraordinary advantages in hosting the edge over the cloud, and dynamic provisioning of VSF at the edge of the network can improve the scalability which is needed to handle the massive IoT traffic. These factors underline the importance of SCO in the IoT. Design and deployment of SCO in IoT with SDN, NFV and edge computing that are optimized for constrained sensing scenarios and can efficiently, reliably deliver the complex and advanced security capabilities are required.

1) Introduction

As shown in Figure 1, SCO implementation in IoT consists of a SCO plane, a security enforcement plane, and an IoT

domain. The IoT domain contains the Cellular IoT Radio Access Network Distributed Unit (CIoT RAN-DU) and the IoT devices to be managed. This includes security enablers, actuators, or VSFs and PSFs needed to monitor the IoT traffic or enforce security instructions coming from the SCO plane [5]. The IoT controller manages these security directives. IoT controllers are close to the network edge, such as gateways. They provide southbound interfaces to manage and control various IoT devices according to the IoT protocols. VSFs such as IDS or virtual monitoring nodes can be stationed on the edge nodes on-demand. These virtual network probes keep track of the IoT devices' traffic and transmit flow statistics and other data to the monitoring module, which activates security alerts in the event of abnormal behaviour or possible threats. The monitoring module sends these security alerts to the reaction module. The reaction module identifies and requests security manager to enforce security measures at IoT nodes using selected enablers during the policy refinement process. The security manager controls the entire process by applying the network security policies issued over the NFV-MANO and SDN controller, dropping, filtering, and diverting network flow, and adjusting the nature of the network following Support Service Level Agreement (SSLA) and available resources. To enable threat countermeasures and defence mechanisms, network security functions such as vAAA, vFirewall, vIDS/IPS, vIoTHoneyNet, and vChannelProtection are implemented as VNFs.

2) Existing works

Several works focus on SCO in IoT environments, leveraging SDN, NFV, and edge computing functionalities. In Zarca et al [3], [6]–[9], propose a novel policy-based security architecture for SDN/NFV-enabled IoT systems. The authors of [6] present a semantic-aware, policy-driven, and zero-touch SCO framework for autonomous and conflict-free SCO in SDN/NFV-enabled IoT systems while maintaining optimal allocation of VSF and SFC. The authors of [3] present a complete architectural framework that addresses the most crucial privacy and security issues of cyber-physical systems and IoT-enabled Critical Infrastructures (IoT-CIs). The architecture was successfully carried out and assessed in the scope of ANASTACIA H2020 EU [10] project.

In [6], [9] focus on managing channel protection and AAA security solutions in IoT networks leveraging SDN and NFV technologies. Network authenticators and virtual AAA are implemented as VNF dynamically at the edge. In [8], authors concentrate on a cutting-edge framework using SDN and NFV to deploy and enforce IoT honeynets automatically. Pablo et al. [11] present a virtualized, multitenant 5G-based IoT traffic filtering security architecture to achieve self-organizing networking capabilities. In [5], the authors extend their previous work and propose an automatic deployment of firewalls by exploiting NFV-MANO to protect Narrow Band (NB)-IoT mMTC communications. A security framework is proposed by Farris et al. [12], [13] to utilize SDN/NFV-aware security

Fig. 1: How security orchestration performed in IoT

features and create a more effective integration with current IoT security and in [13], they build on their earlier work [12], which described the methods for the policy refinement and enforcement processes and assessed the effectiveness of the solution.

Ana et al. [14] proposes an NFV/SDN-aware security management framework with zero-touch capabilities for IoT, where lightweight VSFs are deployed in MEC-UAVs in an orchestrated manner to safeguard and optimize the IoT network, along with replacing and assisting compromised physical equipment such as IoT gateways. Imrith et al. [15] propose a framework to realize dynamic, pragmatic SCO with fog in IoT deployments integrating lightweight virtualization. The authors have launched multiple security instances on the fog infrastructure tested via a Raspberry Pi-4 device. To enable and provide secure and reliable actuation and semi-autonomous behaviour in IoT/IIoT application called SEMI-oTICS, Nikolaos et al. [16] purpose to design a pattern-driven framework on the existing IoT environments. Weissman et al. [16] propose a framework to improve security monitoring in the IoT domain with SCO. Bagaa et al. [17] propose and implement SCO framework leveraging SDN and NFV in an IoT environment. The proposed framework introduces Service Function Chaining (SFC) algorithms. The Life Cycle Management (LCM) model has been optimized considering different

constraints such as QoS, resource availability, security level, and capacities of VNFs.

3) Summary

SCO leverages SDN, NFV, SFC, and edge computing to improve the scalability and flexibility needed for security services in resource-constrained, heterogeneous, and highly dynamic IoT environments. However, SCO in IoT presents some challenges that are being studied by the research community. Some of the key challenges are dynamic and scalable access control (AAA), plug-ins, protocols, and interface definitions between SCO plane and IoT domain (i.e., IoT controller), and monitoring a vast amount of IoT devices. The Extensible Authentication Protocol (EAP) can be used as a framework to enable AAA in IoT networks. Protocol for Carrying Authentication for Network Access (PANA) can carry the EAP payload between the IoT device and the domain controller, providing access to different services and domains [9]. There is no standard way of defining IoT controller plug-ins, interfaces and IoT security policies. Prototype implementations use their own plugins [9], [13], [18]. MQTT, CoAP, REST, HTTPS, and AMQP protocols and message brokers can be used as an interface between the IoT domain and SCO plane for IoT device management, IoT security policy enforcement, and log normalization [19]. Apart from these, allocating resources for SCO might cause performance degradation of applications and services provided. A study needs to be done in this regard to understand the impact. Addressing the above challenges needs a collaborative approach from the industry, regulatory bodies, and research community while developing quality research and innovations in IoT security.

III. PROJECTS/STANDARDS

The significant ongoing research projects and standardization initiatives that directly support SCO in 5G and B5 are presented in this section. Table I summarizes the projects and standardization initiatives and their technical contributions and Fig. 2 gives 5G and B5G Research Projects related to the Security Orchestration.

LF Open Source Component Projects for 5G

Fig. 2: 5G and B5G Research Projects related to the Security Orchestration

SCO aspects/ applications	SCO in NFV	SCO in SDN	SCO in Edge	SCO in IoT	SCO in Slicing	SCO in Cloud	Zero-touch SCO	Multi-Domain SCO
Projects								
SELFNET [20]	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
INSPIRE 5G-Plus [21]	✓	✓			✓		✓	✓
5G-ENSURE [22]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			
ANASTACIA [10]	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
RAINBOW [23]			✓	✓		✓		
MF2C [24]			✓			✓		
Standards								
ETSI	✓	✓					✓	✓
IETF							✓	✓
5G PPP	✓	✓			✓		✓	
NGMN			✓		✓			
IEEE	✓	✓						

TABLE I: Impact of ongoing projects and standards on security orchestration.

A. SELFNET

The SELFNET project [25], part of 5G PPP phase 1, developed an intelligent, self-organized network management framework for SDN and NFV. It integrates technologies like cloud computing, AI, and QoE to reduce manual intervention. Key use cases include: (i) self-defence against cyberattacks, (ii) self-healing, (iii) self-optimization, and (iv) integrated scenarios. Automated monitoring supports proactive network health and maintenance.

B. INSPIRE 5G-PLUS

INSPIRE-5Gplus [21] tackles 5G/B5G cybersecurity via an intelligent, end-to-end, multi-domain security management model. It ensures policy automation and compliance with regulatory standards through Security Management Domains (SMDs), with one SMD dedicated to E2E service protection and trust enforcement.

C. 5G-ENSURE

5G-ENSURE [22], a phase 1 5G PPP project, focused on secure and trustworthy 5G networks. Its main outputs include security enablers, architecture, a testbed, and standardization efforts. Enablers span AAA, trust, privacy, and security management. The project contributed to a holistic trust model and supported 5G standardization activities.

D. ANASTACIA

ANASTACIA [10] developed a comprehensive, standards-compliant security framework for IoT and cloud-based systems. It emphasizes self-healing, self-protection, and dynamic policy orchestration. Use cases target MEC security and smart buildings with support for distributed trust and secure development practices.

E. RAINBOW

RAINBOW [23] aims to deliver a trusted fog computing platform for secure, privacy-preserving IoT-cloud applications. It supports edge-to-cloud trust management and targets critical use cases like industrial robotics, urban mobility, and drone-based infrastructure monitoring.

F. MF2C

MF2C [24] developed a decentralized management framework for fog-to-cloud (F2C) computing. It addresses latency, offloading, privacy, and trust across multi-stakeholder environments. Key use cases include emergency response, navigation services, and smart fog hubs.

G. Open Source Platforms

OpenBaton: Provides an ETSI MANO-compliant framework for orchestrating NSs across heterogeneous NFV infrastructures, supporting autoscaling, fault management, and multi-tenancy [26].

Open Source Mano (OSM): ETSI's Open Source MANO delivers a VIM-independent, operator-ready MANO stack for commercial NFV deployments [27].

Open Network Automation Platform (ONAP): Offers real-time, policy-driven automation and lifecycle management for VNFs and physical network functions in 5G [28].

Open Network Operating System (ONOS): An SDN controller enabling real-time network management for scalable, programmable infrastructures [29].

Open Day Light (ODL): Focuses on SDN-based network programmability, device discovery, security, and automation [30].

H. Standards

Various Standards-Developing Organizations (SDO) are working on standardizing security in 5G and B5G networks. SCO is not yet the focus of these standardization activities. However, some organizations are working in areas that are directly or indirectly relevant to SCO.

ETSI has initiated several Industry Specification Groups (ISG) to research 5G and B5G technologies, including NFV (ETSI NFV), ETSI ISG SAI (Securing Artificial Intelligence), ETSI ISG ENI (Experiential Network Intelligence), and ETSI ISG ZSM. NFV-SEC is a Working Group (WG) under ISG NFV works on all matters related to the relevant security technologies of NFV while producing industry specifications. ETSI ISG SAI focuses on developing standards to preserve and enhance the security of AI [31]. This ISG primarily focuses on three main areas: leveraging AI to improve security, preventing attacks that utilize AI, and protecting AI from attack. ETSI ISG ENI is working to introduce a network management framework, utilizing AI techniques and context-specific policies to modify provided services in response to changes in customer needs, external circumstances, and organizational objectives [32]. This ISG has launched Proof

of Concepts (PoC) to demonstrate how AI techniques assist network operations, including 5G. ETSI ISG ZSM aims to accelerate the design of the necessary E2E framework and solutions for complete E2E automation of network and service management [33]. The main aim of automation is to create entirely autonomous networks controlled by high-level policies and regulations. These networks can be self-monitoring, self-configuration, self-optimization, and self-healing without additional human help. Additionally, it emphasizes the security features of the ZSM architecture and solutions to recognize prospective security threats and mitigation choices that the ZSM requirements take into account to guarantee the security of the automated operations.

Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) Security Automation and Continuous Monitoring (SACM) architecture Request for Comments (RFC) proposes a framework facilitating a cooperative SACM system. This architecture is composed of entities or components. They communicate by exchanging information, in which one or more components are information consumers and one or more components are information sources in a given flow. [34]. The key components are the manager, orchestrator, and repositories. The Manager serves as the SACM ecosystem's control plane, and the orchestrator(s) enables the automation of various tasks like administration, coordination, and configuration of SACM components. Several repositories may exist for posture attribute data, policy data, local vulnerability definition data, and state assessment outcome data.

The 5G PPP Security Work Group (SWG) has been created by 5GPP to support the development of the 5G security community by pro-actively discussing and sharing information [35]. 5G PPP SWG aims to tackle 5G security vulnerabilities and challenges through joint discussions and collaborations. The critical areas of attention are the 5G security architecture and its integration with the 3GPP, privacy, access control, trust, standardization of 5G security, slicing, and security monitoring and management. The group's outcomes, like situational awareness, intelligent network security, and virtualization, directly affect SCO in 5G and B5G networks.

The NGMN 5G E2E architectural framework version 4.3.1 (2020) lists the necessary entities and functions for an E2E framework's capabilities [36]. It also gives an overview of security considerations for safeguarding the various features and enabling capabilities from an E2E perspective for the 5G service paradigm. Application, user, and network domain security, network access security, visibility, and configurability of security are among the several security elements in a 5G system.

Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) P1915.1 standard for SDN and NFV security aims to facilitate a security framework that specifies system models, analytics, and requirements for SDN and NFV [37]. This standard offers a framework for creating and managing more secure SDN/NFV environments for different network stakeholders.

Furthermore, the IEEE P1917.1 standard for SDN and NFV reliability works on developing a framework and requirement for reliable service delivery in SDN/NFV infrastructure [38].

IV. LESSONS LEARNED

A. Lessons learnt

Many research projects and standardization bodies contribute to 5G and B5G security efforts with their technical contributions, security recommendations, and specifications. However, the particular work directly related to SCO is not that much, and standards for the SCO are still in development. Fully standardization of SCO might take a few more years involving several stakeholders such as governments, regulators, operators, policy-makers, manufacturers, and representatives of 5G and B5G users. To fully realize SCO in 5G and B5G networks, integration and coordination across various working groups and SDOs are crucial.

B. Remaining open issues

- How to address the lack of standardization related to SCO?
- How to identify and prioritize the areas related to SCO which needed more focus and attention from research communities and SDOs?
- How to achieve integration and cooperation between different working groups and SDOs?
- How to enable cross-technology SCO in 5G and achieve standard interface definitions?
- How to ensure that future technologies can be easily integrated and adopted into SCO?
- How to integrate SCO as a critical component of standardization work related to 5G and B5G technologies like SDN, NFV, MEC, and network slicing?

C. Future directions

5G and B5G security projects such as SELFNET, INSPIRE 5G-Plus, 5G-ENSURE, ANASTACIA, RAINBOW, MF2C and some open source projects work directly or indirectly on SCO and contribute to the security of the associated technologies. Working groups for 5G and B5G security standards, including ETSI, NGMN, 5G PPP, IEEE and IETF, are developing security recommendations and technical specifications and defining security architectures and concepts that are either directly or indirectly related to SCO. These efforts can be seen as a first step towards the standardization of SCO. However, there is still a long way to go and further efforts are needed from the research community and SDOs to commercialize SCO. Furthermore, collaboration between different research groups and SDOs is of utmost importance.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we have explored the taxonomy of orchestration technologies and their crucial role in securing the IoT in the context of 5G networks. We analyzed the contributions of various projects, open source platforms and standardization

efforts and highlighted their influence on the evolution of orchestration in complex, multi-domain environments. Sustainability and scalability were identified as key challenges, with proposed solutions such as self-sustaining networks and modular metasurface antennas offering promising directions for future progress. Despite significant progress, unresolved challenges remain, including the need for unified orchestration frameworks, improved security integrations and innovative strategies to meet the growing demands of IoT and 5G ecosystems. Future research should focus on closing these gaps by developing holistic approaches that integrate sustainability, scalability and security and ensure resilient and adaptable orchestration for next-generation networks.

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